

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

EOM4SOIL - Deliverable D4.4
Report of N₂O emissions from new EOMs

Due date of deliverable: M57 (October 2024)
Actual submission date: 10.10.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	D4.4
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Report of N2O emissions from new EOMs
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP4
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	C balance and gas emission
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	CREA
AUTHOR:	Roberta Pastorelli, Alessandra Lagomarsino, Claudio Mondini, Ana Cervera-Mata, Nadia Vignozzi, Ferdinand Hartmann
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14056164
LICENSE	CC BY 4.0
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	CO/PU (Until the associated peer-reviewed papers have been published)

ABSTRACT

The objective of this deliverable is to provide data on the N₂O emissions from soil following the application of new external organic matter (EOM). The results are based on two mesocosms experiments conducted by CREA (Italy) and a field experiment led by BOKU (Austria). The first mesocosm study assessed the impact of soil amendments with digestate and biochar, produced by LUKE (Finland) as a part of the WP2 activity, on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, soil carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) content, and microbial communities. The second laboratory experiment studied the effect of different amendments produced from spent coffee grounds (compost, biochar and hydrochar) on soil C and N cycles, element availability, microbial biomass content and GHG emissions. The field experiment evaluated the short-term effects of compost, biochar, and digestate on N₂O emissions and NH₃ volatilization during silage maize cultivation.

Results of first mesocosm experiment showed that digestate effectively acted as a fertilizer, while biochar application reduced the presence of Clostridiaceae in soil but unexpectedly increased N₂O emissions at higher concentrations. CO₂ emissions increased with digestate application but decreased with a 10% biochar concentration, aligning with control levels. CH₄ uptake decreased with digestate and high biochar concentrations. The second mesocosm experiment showed a clear relationship between the properties of the amendments and their effect on soil functioning and GHG emissions. N₂O emission factors were lower than 0.01% of added N and related to the degradability and the N content of the materials. The field experiment suggested two mechanisms for N₂O emission reduction: nitrate and ammonium immobilization in soil and enhanced denitrification facilitated by biochar, with the latter well-supported by existing literature.

The findings underscore the importance of tailored approaches, considering biochar composition and dosage, to optimize soil greenhouse gas fluxes and microbial communities. This report contributes valuable data for comprehensive assessments of the EOM impacts on mitigating climate change and improving soil health and ecosystem functioning. Such insights are crucial for promoting sustainable agriculture within the circular bioeconomy framework.

Table of Contents

List of Tables.....	5
List of Figures.....	5
List of acronyms and abbreviations.....	6
1. Introduction.....	7
2. Mesocosm experiment 1.....	8
2.1. Materials and Methods.....	8
2.1.1. Experimental setup	8
2.1.2. GHG emissions and soil analysis	9
2.2. Results and Discussion	11
2.2.1. Changes in soil properties	11
2.2.2. GHG emissions	13
2.2.3. Microbial communities	15
2.3. Conclusions	16
3. Mesocosm experiment 2.....	16
3.1. Materials and Methods.....	16
3.1.1. Materials	16
3.1.2. Mesocosm experiment setup.....	17
3.1.3. GHG emissions and soil analysis	17
3.2. Results and Discussion	18
3.2.1. Changes in soil properties	18
3.2.2. GHG emissions	20
3.3. Conclusions	22
4. Field experiment	22
4.1. Materials and Methods.....	22
4.1.1. Experimental setup	22
4.1.2. Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O) emissions	23
4.1.3. Ammonia (NH ₃) volatilisation.....	23
4.1.4. Soil measurements.....	25
4.2. Most relevant results	25
4.3. Conclusions	30
List of references.....	31
Annex.....	35
Appendix 1. Data sheet: N ₂ O emissions from mesocosms	35

List of Tables

Table 1: Chemical characteristics of cattle manure, digestates (Tampio et al., 2024) and biochar (n.d. = not determined) (Pastorelli et al., 2024)	8
Table 2: Primer pairs used for real time PCR absolute quantification of the different microbial groups assessed in soil of the different mesocosms	11
Table 3: Fisher's LSD post hoc test ($p < 0.05$) of cumulative emissions of CO ₂ , CH ₄ and N ₂ O. Mean values of each flux are reported as $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ (standard error in parenthesis). Different letters indicate significant differences among treatments.....	13
Table 4: Chemical properties of SCG and SCG by-products	16
Table 5: NO ₃ ⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺ and net mineral N at the end of incubation	20
Table 6: Soil treatment in Short-Term Experiment	222

List of Figures

Figure 1: Jars for mesocosms' setting up (A) and GASMET FTIR-gas analyzer (B)	9
Figure 2: Mesocosms set up with various combinations of soil, digestate and biochar.....	10
Figure 3: Chemical properties of soil at the end of mesocosm experiments.....	122
Figure 4: Potential production/consumption of CO ₂ (top), CH ₄ (middle) and N ₂ O (bottom) in control soils, and after addition of digestate R1 and R2 (Dig1 and Dig2) and/or 2% and 10% of biochar (Dig1+bio2%, Dig2+bio2%, Dig1+bio10%, Dig2+bio10%) during the 22 days of incubation	144
Figure 5: Relative abundance of the target nitrifying (<i>amoA</i>) and denitrifying (<i>nirK</i> , <i>nirS</i> , and <i>nosZ</i>) microbial groups versus bacterial 16S rDNA.....	155
Figure 6: Mesocosm incubation experiment set up.....	177
Figure 7: Gas chromatography system for automated sampling and measurement of GHG fluxes from incubated soil mesocosms	188
Figure 8: Extractable organic C and N in the control and amended soil.....	199
Figure 9: Soil microbial biomass C and N in control and amended soil	199
Figure 10: Nitrate and available P in control and amended soil	20
Figure 11: Cumulative CO ₂ -C and N ₂ O-N emissions in control and amended soil	211
Figure 12: Relationships between cumulative emissions of CO ₂ -C and N ₂ O-N.....	21
Figure 13: Field experiment Grabenegg.....	233
Figure 14: N ₂ O measurements, static chamber (A) and linear regression of measured N ₂ O emissions (B)	233
Figure 15: NH ₃ -measurements: semi-open static chamber	244
Figure 16: NH ₃ -measurements with Picarro ammonia in ambient air analyser.....	25
Figure 17: Opentrons pipetting robot	25
Figure 18: Nitrogen data: soil-NO ₃ ⁻ , soil-NH ₄ ⁺ , N ₂ O emissions, NH ₃ volatilisation and soil moisture. ..	26
Figure 19: N ₂ O emissions maize (season 2022).....	26
Figure 20: NH ₃ volatilisation maize (season 2022).....	27
Figure 21: Soil nitrate maize (season 2022).	27
Figure 22: Soil ammonium maize (season 2022).....	288
Figure 23: N ₂ O emissions and NH ₃ volatilisation wheat (season 2023).	28
Figure 24: Soil nitrate and ammonium, wheat (season 2023)	29
Figure 25: N ₂ O emissions maize (season 2024).....	29
Figure 26: NH ₃ volatilisation maize (season 2024).....	29
Figure 27: Soil nitrate maize (season 2024).	30
Figure 28: Soil ammonium maize (season 2024).....	30

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AD	Anaerobic digestion
AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
BVOC	Biogenic volatile organic compound
CREA	Council for Agricultural Research and Agricultural Economics
EC	Electrical Conductivity
EOC	Extractable organic carbon
EOM	External Organic Matter
EN	Extractable nitrogen
FTIR	Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
HC	Hydrochar
HTC	Hydrothermal carbonization
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
LSD	Fisher's Least Significant Difference
LUKE	Natural Resources Institute Finland
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PTFE	Polytetrafluorethylen
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
SCG	Spent coffee grounds
SNK	Student Newman Keuls
TC	Total Carbon
TN	Total Nitrogen
TOC	Total Organic carbon
TS	Total solid
VC	Vermicompost
VS	Volatile solid
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The emissions of gases like nitrous oxide (N₂O) and ammonia (NH₃) after applying external organic matter (EOM) to soil can vary significantly based on agricultural practices, environmental conditions, and the specific EOM used. Sustainable management practices that optimize organic inputs while reducing losses are crucial for combating climate change. These methods not only lower greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) but also repurpose by-products traditionally seen as waste into valuable resources (Mondini et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2022).

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is central to the circular economy, converting organic waste into renewable biogas and producing digestate, a nutrient-rich byproduct that enhances soil quality and fertility. Through AD, organic nitrogen (N) is converted into ammonium (NH₄⁺-N) and phosphorus into orthophosphate, making these nutrients more readily available to plants and reducing the need for mineral fertilizers (Ren et al., 2020; Mickan et al., 2022). Digestate also adds carbon (C) to the soil, improving its physical properties (Pastorelli et al., 2021). Compost, another key product in organic waste recycling, undergoes aerobic decomposition, unlike digestate, and is widely used to improve soil health. Rich in organic matter, compost increases soil fertility by gradually releasing nutrients, stimulating microbial activity, and improving soil structure. The combination of compost with digestate can optimize nutrient supply and soil C levels, offering a balanced approach to organic soil amendments. Additionally, compost helps in reducing soil erosion, enhancing water retention, and suppressing plant diseases, further supporting sustainable agricultural practices (Abdullahi et al., 2008). Biochar, produced from organic materials through pyrolysis or gasification, is another valuable soil amendment that sequesters C long-term and reduces soil emissions of N₂O and methane (CH₄) (Plaimart et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021). It also improves soil structure, promotes aggregation, and enhances water retention, making it effective for climate change mitigation (Cayuela et al., 2014). All these EOM contribute to the circular bioeconomy by recycling nutrients. However, their use can alter microbial habitats and affect soil bacterial communities and processes like N-mineralization and NH₃-oxidation (Ren et al., 2020).

The EOM4SOIL project focuses on understanding how EOM can mitigate climate change, improve soil quality, and reduce the reliance on mineral fertilizers. This report summarizes results from 2 mesocosm experiments (Cervera et al., 2022; Pastorelli et al., 2024) carried out by CREA (Italy) using EOMs from manure and sludge produced by LUKE (Finland) and spent coffee grounds derived amendments (such as compost, biochar and hydrochar), as well as a field experiment led by BOKU (Austria) at Grabenegg station (lower Austria). The first study evaluates the effects of digestate and biochar on greenhouse gas emissions, soil carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) content, and microbial communities, shedding light on the benefits and risks of these soil amendments in agriculture. The second laboratory experiment studied the effect of different amendments produced from spent coffee grounds on soil C and N cycles, element availability, microbial biomass content and GHG emissions. The field experiment focused on silage maize cultivation and examined the short-term effects of applying compost, biochar, a compost-biochar mixture, and biogas digestate on N₂O and NH₃ soil emissions.

This research supports sustainability and the circular bioeconomy principles by promoting environmentally friendly practices that reduce waste and improve resource efficiency.

This document specifically focuses on Task 4.1, which involves the creation of a database for N₂O, BVOC, and NH₃ emissions following EOM application. In particular, this document aligns with the goals of Sub Task 4.1.2. “Additional measurements in mesocosms under controlled conditions and field experiments”, contributing to the implementation of the database on N₂O from soil using the EOM tested in WP2.

2. Mesocosm experiment 1

2.1. Materials and Methods

2.1.1. Experimental setup

Two manure-based digestates obtained from parallel 1 m³ batch-type leach-bed reactors (R1 and R2), and biochar produced at temperature of 565 °C and treatment time of 75 min from a mixture of digested sewage sludge and waste wood (80%/20% mass ratio, respectively) were used (Tampio et al., 2024). The chemical characteristics of the EOMs are provided in Table 1.

The soil was collected in April 2023 from the 0–20 cm plow layer of an agricultural field at Fagna experimental farm in Scarperia, Firenze, Italy. Classified as Fluventic Eutrudept with a loam texture (30% sand, 44% silt, 26% clay), it was air-dried and sieved to remove debris, making it ready for the experiment.

Table 1: Chemical characteristics of cattle manure, digestates (Tampio et al., 2024) and biochar (n.d. = not determined) (Pastorelli et al., 2024).

		Digestate R1	Digestate R2	Biochar
Total solid (TS)	%	12.5	12.9	98.
Volatile solid (VS)	% (TS)	83.5	85.4	29.8
Carbon (C)	% (TS)	46.0	46.1	29.8
Hydrogen (H)	% (TS)	4.8	5.3	0.3
Nitrogen (N)	% (TS)	2.0	2.0	2.4
Sulfur (S)	% (TS)	0.3	0.3	1.6
Oxygen (O)	% (TS)	30.3	31.6	-2.2
Ash	% (TS)	16.5	14.6	68.1
Phosphorous (P)	% (TS)	3.1	2.7	53.7
Potassium (K)	% (TS)	38.7	38.7	2.2
Calcium (Ca)	% (TS)	7.7	8.5	31.3
Iron (Fe)	% (TS)	1.5	2.4	246.0
Magnesium (Mg)	% (TS)	5.3	5.3	3.6
Sodium (Na)	% (TS)	1.9	1.7	1.1
Ammonium N (NH₄-N)	% (TS)	8.0	6.2	0.4
Total Kjeldahl N (TNK)	% (TS)	23.9	21.7	n.d.

The mesocosm experiment utilized 1000 cm³ polyethylene jars (80 cm² surface area; 12.5 cm height), each containing 0.5 Kg of dry soil (Figure 1A). The soil was amended with the digestate and/or biochar and jars were incubated under controlled temperature. A total of 27 jars were set up to test 9 different treatments: control (soil without EOM), soil with digestate (150 N Kg ha⁻¹), soil with biochar (2% or 10%), soil with both digestate and biochar (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Jars for mesocosms' setting up(A) and GASMET FTIR-gas analyzer (B).

Soil water content was maintained at approximately 35% of field capacity by watering the jars after each GHG measurement. The jars were incubated in darkness at a controlled temperature of 20 °C for 3 weeks.

2.1.2. GHG emissions and soil analysis

The potential production of GHGs (CO₂, N₂O, CH₄) was estimated at various intervals during the 22-day incubation using a portable Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)-based gas analyzer GASMET DX4040 (Gasetm Technology Oy) (Figure 1B) connected to jar by Teflon tubes. Measurements were taken every minute for 10 minutes, with background calibration with pure N (99.999%) performed before each session (Pastorelli et al., 2024). Gas concentrations (ppm) were converted to mass per volume units using the Ideal Gas Law, accounting for air temperature and volume, and expressed in mmol g⁻¹ based on jar headspace soil sample weight (Lagomarsino et al., 2024). The cumulative emissions were determined by summing concentrations at each incubation time.

At the end of experimentation, soil parameters were determined by standard protocol analysis and DNA was extracted from 0.5 g of soil using the FAST DNA SPIN kit for SOIL (MP Biomedicals, Solon, OH, USA). Real-time PCR was performed using specific primers (Table 2) for 16S ribosomal DNA (bacteria and Clostridiaceae) and marker genes related to functional microbial groups involved in carbon and nitrogen cycles (e.g., *mcrA* for methanogens, *pmoA* for methanotrophs, *amoA* for nitrifiers, and *nirK*, *nirS*, and *nosZ* for denitrifiers) (Pastorelli et al., 2024).

GHGs cumulative emissions, chemical analysis, and DNA amplifications were conducted on individual replicates, with results expressed as the mean and standard error. Statistical significance was assessed using ANOVA followed by Fisher's least Significant Difference (LSD) post-hoc test ($p < 0.05$), using Statistica 7 software. Normality and variance homogeneity were verified prior to ANOVA.

Figure 2: Mesocosms set up with various combinations of soil, digestate and biochar.

Table 2: Primer pairs used for real time PCR absolute quantification of the different microbial groups assessed in soil of the different mesocosms.

Target microbial group	Target gene	Primer	Annealing Temperature	Reference
Bacteria	16S rRNA	Bac341F Bac805R	60°C	Muyzer et al. (1993) Caporaso et al. (2011)
Clostridiaceae cluster I and II	16S rRNA	CHIS150F CLOST1R	55°C	Hung et al (2008) Green et al (2011)
Clostridiaceae cluster IV	16S rRNA	CLEPF CLEPR	60°C	Zwiehler et al. (2009)
Methanogenic archaea	<i>mcrA</i>	qmcrAF qmcrAR	60°C	Denman et al. (2007)
Methanotrophic bacteria	<i>pmoA</i>	A189F Mb661R	60°C	Kolb et al. (2003)
Nitrifying bacteria	<i>amoA</i>	AmoA1F AmoA1R	57°C	Xu et al. (2012)
Nitrifying archaea	<i>amoA</i>	archamoAF archamoAR	55°C	Xu et al. (2012)
Denitrifying bacteria	<i>nirK</i>	F1ACu R3Cu	57°C	Throbäck et al. (2004)
Denitrifying bacteria	<i>nirS</i>	Cd3aF1 R3Cd	52°C	Throbäck et al. (2004)
Denitrifying bacteria	<i>nosZ</i>	nosZF nosZ1733R	55°C	Throbäck et al. (2004)

2.2. Results and Discussion

2.2.1. Changes in soil properties

After the incubation period, most chemical parameters increased with the addition of 2% and 10% biochar to the soil (Figure 3). Total carbon (TC), TOC, TN, and electrical conductivity (EC) significantly increased in soil amended with 10% biochar, regardless of digestate addition, potentially posing risks of phytotoxicity effects for more sensitive crops.

No significant differences were observed between the control, digestate, and 2% biochar treatments. Soil pH values ranged from 7.8 to 8.0 across treatments, with a slight decrease associated with biochar addition.

Figure 3: Chemical properties of soil at the end of mesocosm experiments. Error bars calculated as standard errors. Different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$ (Fisher's least Significant Difference, LSD).

2.2.2. GHG emissions

Adding digestates to soil significantly increased CO₂ emissions (Fig. 4, top), with no difference between the two samples tested. Biochar had a dose-dependent effect: it caused a significant increase in CO₂ emissions at lower concentration (2%) and led to a substantial reduction at higher concentration (10%) (Table 3). At lower concentrations, biochar may boost microbial activity by providing a substrate for growth and enhancing nutrient availability (Gomez et al., 2014). However, at higher concentrations, biochar may inhibit microbial metabolic activities or slow down the rate of C-turnover (Thies et al., 2015).

During incubation, CH₄ uptake was predominant (Fig. 4, middle), nearing zero after 2 weeks in samples with digestate and biochar. While CH₄ uptake remained high overall, biochar reduced it (Table 3), likely by affecting methanotrophic activity rather than abundance (He et al., 2017). Digestate increased CH₄-producing microorganisms, but biochar helped mitigate CH₄ emissions by promoting aerobic conditions that favour CH₄-consuming microbes.

N₂O production (Fig. 4, bottom) was minimal in control soils but increased significantly with digestate and 10% biochar (Table 3). The combination of digestate + biochar showed contrasting effects: a reduction to control levels at 2% and a sharp increase (about 3 times higher than digestate alone) at 10%. This elevated N₂O emission at higher doses is likely attributed to inhibited N mineralization and nitrification, leading to incomplete denitrification and increased N₂O release (Cayuela et al., 2014). However, the biochar used in this study, characterized by high N and low C content, may have contributed to increased N₂O emissions. Its inability to support the colonization of denitrifying bacteria further explains the reduced efficiency in N₂O reduction (Zhao et al., 2023; Thomson et al., 2012).

Table 3: Fisher's LSD post hoc test ($p < 0.05$) of cumulative emissions of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O. Mean values of each flux are reported as $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ (standard error in parenthesis). Different letters indicate significant differences among treatments.

Treatment	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O
Control	3.30 (0.7) c	-0.30 (0.02) c	0.53 (0.12) d
Dig1	4.97 (0.8) bc	-0.26 (0.04) c	2.79 (0.27) cd
Dig2	3.97 (0.1) bc	-0.15 (0.01) b	2.99 (0.10) cd
Bio2%	7.79 (1.4) b	-0.16 (0.01) b	1.88 (0.57) cd
Bio10%	1.44 (0.1) c	-0.13 (0.01) b	9.48 (2.1) b
Dig1+bio2%	17.98 (2.8) a	-0.11 (0.01) b	3.97 (0.19) c
Dig2+bio2%	16.30 (3.2) a	-0.14 (0.01) b	3.63 (0.69) c
Dig1+bio10%	1.56 (0.1) c	-0.02 (0.01) a	13.65 (2.33) a
Dig2+bio10%	1.63 (0.3) c	-0.03 (0.01) a	13.16 (1.94) a

Figure 4: Potential production/consumption of CO₂ (top), CH₄ (middle) and N₂O (bottom) in control soils, and after addition of digestate R1 and R2 (Dig1 and Dig2) and/or 2% and 10% of biochar (Dig1+bio2%, Dig2+bio2%, Dig1+bio10%, Dig2+bio10%) during the 22 days of incubation. Error bars calculated as standard errors in replicate mesocosms. Different letters indicate significant differences at p < 0.05 (Fisher's least Significant Difference, LSD).

2.2.3. Microbial communities

Bacterial 16S rRNA gene abundance ranged between $7.6 \times 10^9 \pm 7.2 \times 10^8$ (soil added with 10% biochar) and 1.3×10^{10} copy dry soil g^{-1} . Treatment significantly affected the relative abundance of nitrifying, denitrifying, and methanotrophic microbial groups, although no clear direct link between bacterial abundance and treatment was found (Fig 5). Unlike some studies, nitrifier and denitrifier populations were not significantly affected, possibly due to the short incubation period. Longer-term studies might reveal more pronounced effects on microbial functions and N-cycling.

In soils amended with digestate, there was a significant increase in the abundance of methanogenic archaea and Clostridiaceae (Fig. 5). However, the addition of biochar led to a reduction in Clostridiaceae, suggesting its potential to mitigate the microbial impacts associated with digestate spreading (Al Seadi et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2021). Although *Clostridium* species are naturally present in soil, there's ongoing debate about the risks of repeated digestate use due to potential pathogen presence (Pulvirenti et al., 2015).

Figure 5: Relative abundance of the target nitrifying (*amoA*) and denitrifying (*nirK*, *nirS*, and *nosZ*) microbial groups versus bacterial 16S rDNA. Error bars calculated as standard errors in replicate mesocosms. Different letters indicate significant differences (Fisher's least Significant Difference, LSD).

2.3. Conclusions

This mesocosm experiment highlights the complex interactions between biochar, digestate, and soil microbial processes, with significant implications for sustainable agriculture. Biochar demonstrated contrasting effects on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with biochar reducing CH₄ uptake but increasing N₂O emissions at higher concentrations, likely due to altered nitrification and denitrification processes.

Microbial community shifts, particularly the rise of Clostridiaceae in digestate-amended soils, raise potential concerns about pathogen risks, although biochar showed effectiveness in reducing their abundance. The observed short-term changes in microbial abundance and function suggest that longer incubation periods may be necessary to fully understand the impacts of biochar and digestate on soil microbial dynamics.

Overall, the study underscores the critical role of biochar composition and dosage in influencing soil GHG fluxes, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to optimize its impact on microbial communities and nutrient availability. It also emphasizes the need for a balanced approach when integrating biochar and digestate into agricultural systems, ensuring benefits for crop production while mitigating environmental risks.

3. Mesocosm experiment 2

3.1. Materials and Methods

3.1.1. Materials

In this experiment spent coffee grounds (SCG), obtained from a cafeteria, and eight SCG-derived byproducts were utilized. The SCG derived by-products were: biochar produced at 270°C (BC 270) and 400°C (BC 400), hydrochar produced at 160°C (HC 160) and 200°C (HC 200), vermicompost (VC), defatted SCG (D SCG) and two biochar from defatted SCG (produced at 270°C and 400°C, D BC 270 and D BC 400, respectively). Biochars were produced in a pyrolytic oven (Navertherm GmbH, Germany) in two different ways: 270 °C for 60 min and 400 °C for 30 min. The hydrochars were generated in a laboratory-scale hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) reactor (Highpreactor™ BR-300, Berghof Ltd, Germany). The vermicompost derived from SCG were supplied by organic natural fertilizer company The vermicomposting of SCG was performed for 8 months using Californian red earthworm (*Eisenia foetida*). The defatting of SCG was performed by lipids extraction with hexane during 3 h in a Soxhlet apparatus, in order to improve the performance of the pyrolysis process. The chemical properties of the amendments are reported in table 4.

Table 4. Chemical properties of SCG and SCG by-products.

Residue	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	pH	EC ₂₅ (dS m ⁻¹)	LOI (%)	C (%)	N (%)	C/N	WSC (µg g ⁻¹)	WSN (µg g ⁻¹)	N-NH ₄ ⁺ (µg g ⁻¹)	N-NO ₃ ⁻ (µg g ⁻¹)
SCG	7.5	1.4	5.4	9.0	98.6	48.0	2.3	21	26	3.7	12	2.6
BC 270	4.1	2.1	6.4	3.1	97.9	58.1	3.2	18	6.6	0.7	7.6	nd
BC 400	2.5	3.7	8.4	1.8	96.5	69.8	4.2	16	0.6	0.5	3.1	nd
HC 160	3.6	0.4	4.6	4.4	99.6	52.0	2.2	24	31	3.8	160	6.4
HC 200	3.5	0.5	3.9	4.2	99.5	62.6	2.5	25	38	4.7	47	1.3
VC	10.4	19	7.8	48.3	80.1	40.6	5.8	7	11	3.0	58	22
D SCG	8.0	1.6	5.4	11.2	98.4	48.8	2.6	19	26	4.0	20	1.1
D BC 270	4.8	3.1	5.9	5.6	96.5	63.0	4.1	15	4.7	0.6	13	nd
D BC 400	4.1	2.8	8.6	2.2	97.7	72.2	4.5	16	0.9	0.2	3.0	nd

SCG: spent coffee grounds; D SCG: defatted SCG; BC 270: biochar produced at 270°C; VC: vermicompost; HC 160: hydrochar produced at 160°C; HC 200: hydrochar produced at 200°C; D BC 270: biochar from defatted SCG produced at 270°C; BC 400: biochar produced at 400°C; D BC 400: biochar from defatted SCG produced at 400°C.

The soil used in the incubations was sampled from the arable layer (0 - 20 cm) of an agricultural soil from the Vega of Granada (Andalusia, Southern Spain). The soil class was classified as Cambic Calcisol (Aric, Ochric) (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2014) and presents the following properties: sand 281 g kg⁻¹, clay 580 g kg⁻¹, silt 139 g kg⁻¹, moisture 410 g kg⁻¹, pH 8.2, OC 13.6 g kg⁻¹, total N 1.05 g kg⁻¹, C/N 13, carbonates as CaCO₃ 390 g kg⁻¹, available K 453 mg kg⁻¹, available P 69 mg kg⁻¹. Soil samples were air-dried and sieved (2 mm).

3.1.2. Mesocosm experiment setup

Before the experiment, the soil was pre-conditioned at 40% of water holding capacity and 20 °C under aerobic conditions for 5 days. Subsequently, the residues were thoroughly added at the dose of 2.5% (w:w) and aerobically incubated in the dark at 20 °C for 21 days. Untreated soil was also included as a control. Samples were incubated in sealed plastic jars for determination of CO₂ and N₂O evolution every 4 hours (in triplicate), while an identical parallel incubation was set out for determination after 21 days of extractable organic C (EOC), N (EN), NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, and available P and soil microbial biomass C and N content (Figure 6). The moisture levels in the jars were checked weekly by measuring weight loss, and deionised water was added when necessary to maintain constant moisture.

Figure 6. Mesocosm incubation experiment set up.

3.1.3. GHG emissions and soil analysis

CO₂ and N₂O evolution were determined by an automated system for continuous gas sampling and analysis. The system operates as an “open chamber” system in which the sealed plastic jars containing the soil sample are continuously aerated at constant flow rate (15 ml min⁻¹). The output of all jars is vented to the ambient, except for a selected jar which output is directed by means of two valves to a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7890A) for GHG content (CO₂ and N₂O) determination. At the end of the measurement period (6 min), the valves automatically direct the output of the following jar to the GC

and so on. The system can operate with up to 30 samples and allows the measurement of the evolution rate of greenhouse gases over regular periods (figure 7).

Figure 7. Gas chromatography system for automated sampling and measurement of GHG fluxes from incubated soil mesocosms.

Extractable organic C, N, NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻, were determined following extraction using a 1:4 (w/v) ratio of soil to K₂SO₄ 0.5 M extract. K₂SO₄-extractable organic C (EOC) and N (EN) were measured using a TOC-TN analyzer (TOC-VCSN Shimadzu). Extractable NH₄⁺ was determined by a modified colorimetric method based on Berthelot's reaction and performed in microplate (Sommer et al., 1992). The content of NO₃⁻ was measured by a modified colorimetric method based on VCl₃-Griess reaction (Miranda et al. 2001). Available P was determined by a colorimetric method (Van Veldhoven and Mannaerts, 1987). Soil microbial biomass C (B_C) and N (B_N) were determined by the fumigation-extraction method (Vance et al., 1987).

Means between groups were compared by analysis of variance (ANOVA) at p < 0.05 confidence level (SNK test). Linear correlations were evaluated by computing the correlation coefficient by Pearson. These statistical procedures were carried out using SPSS 15.0 for Windows (IBM SPSS Inc., New York, USA).

3.2. Results and Discussion

3.2.1. Changes in soil properties

The addition of SCG by-products increased significantly EOC with respect to the control, except for the 4 biochars (Figure 8). The highest values of EOC were recorded for the two hydrochars produced at 160 °C. The EOC can provide an indication of the stability of the amendments towards decomposition in soil. Therefore, HCs are the more degradable ones, followed by HCs and VC. On the other side, all BCs are quite stable as they did not cause an increase in extractable OC. The high degradability of hydrochars is likely attributable to the fact that the hydrothermal carbonization process results in the presence of less polyaromatic C and the predominance of aliphatic compounds, properties of a material with low stability (Kammann et al., 2022).

The only treatment that increased EN with respect to the control, was VC. On the contrary, the addition of all other materials caused a significant decrease of EN (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Extractable organic C and N in the control and amended soil. Error bars indicate standard deviation. Different letters denote significant differences (SNK post-hoc test).

The addition of SCG by-products, increased the content of B_C and B_N (Figure 9) with the only exception of the two biochars produced at 400 °C. The two spent coffee grounds had the larger impact on the size of the microbial biomass, followed by the two biochars produced at 270 °C and the hydrochars.

Figure 9. Soil microbial biomass C and N in control and amended soil. Error bars indicate standard deviation. Different letters denote significant differences (SNK post-hoc test).

Among the treatments showing a significant increase in microbial biomass, VC showed the smaller one. The response of soil microbial biomass is related to the stability of the materials as indicated by cumulative CO₂ evolution. Microbial biomass C and N were significantly correlated with CO₂-C emissions expressed as percentage of added C ($r = 0.88$ and 0.81 , $P < 0.05$ respectively), indicating that the degree of degradability of the added residues has a strong impact on the size of the microbial biomass.

Regarding the addition of SCG by products on the availability of the nutrients, soil amendment significantly modified the content of nitrate (Figure 10), while no effect was recorded for ammonium (data not shown). Soil amendment caused a decrease in NO₃⁻ in all the treatments except VC. The larger decreases were recorded for the more decomposable materials i.e. SCG and HC for which NO₃⁻ content was near to 0.

Figure 10. Nitrate and available P in control and amended soil. Error bars indicate standard deviation. Different letters denote significant differences (SNK post-hoc test).

As a consequence, the net mineral N presented a negative balance in all cases, except for VC sample. The most negative balances were recorded for SCG, HC and D BC 270 (Table 5). These results indicate that all amendments, but VC caused N immobilization, although with a different extent. In particular, larger N immobilization was found for the amendments showing higher degradability and relatively high C/N ratio. i.e. SCGs and HCs.

Table 5. NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺ and net mineral N at the end of incubation.

Sample	N-NO ₃ ⁻ (µg g ⁻¹)	N-NH ₄ ⁺ (µg g ⁻¹)	Net mineral N (µg N g ⁻¹)
Control	37.6 ^e	1.0 ^a	-
SCG	0.7 ^a	1.3 ^a	-36.6 ^a
D SCG	0.7 ^a	1.6 ^a	-36.3 ^a
VC	46.2 ^f	1.5 ^a	9.1 ^d
HC 160	0.9 ^a	2.7 ^b	-35.0 ^a
HC 200	0.8 ^a	1.6 ^a	-36.3 ^a
BC 270	6.4 ^b	1.4 ^a	-30.8 ^a
D BC 270	20.3 ^c	1.4 ^a	-17.0 ^b
BC 400	31.2 ^d	1.5 ^a	-6.0 ^c
D BC 400	28.9 ^d	1.4 ^a	-8.3 ^c

SCG: spent coffee grounds; D SCG: defatted SCG; BC 270: biochar produced at 270°C; VC: vermicompost; HC 160: hydrochar produced at 160°C; HC 200: hydrochar produced at 200°C; D BC 270: biochar from defatted SCG produced at 270°C; BC 400: biochar produced at 400°C; D BC 400: biochar from defatted SCG produced at 400°C. In the same column, different letters indicated significant differences among treatments according to a SNK post-hoc test ($p < 0.05$).

For that concerning the availability of P, the only amendments causing an increase were VC and to lower extent BC 270 from defatted spent coffee grounds (Figure 10).

3.2.2. GHG emissions

Amendment with SCG and SCG derived by products resulted in a significant increase in CO₂ emissions, with the exception of the biochars produced at 400 °C that did not alter the respiratory response of the soil (Figure 11). The larger increases were recorded for SCGs and HCs, while a lower increase was recorded for BCs at 270 °C and VC. These results allow to classify the amendments in 3 main groups concerning their degradability. SCG and HC were highly degradable material (CO₂-C mineralized about 10 % of added C), BC at 270 °C and VC showed a low degradability (CO₂-C mineralized 1-3% of added

C). Biochar at 400 °C showed an extreme stability as the amount of CO₂ released from the amendments was under the detection limit of the measurement system.

Figure 11. Cumulative CO₂-C and N₂O-N emissions in control and amended soil. Error bars indicate standard deviation. Different letters denote significant differences (SNK post-hoc test).

Addition caused a significant increase in N₂O with respect to the control only for 5 amendments, namely SCGs, HCs produced at 160°C and VC. The defatting treatment did not affect the N₂O emissions. The percentage of N emitted as N₂O with respect to the added N was very low being at maximum 0.1%. Results showed that these materials do not represent an environmental concern when applied to soil for that considering N₂O emissions. On the other site results shows that there is a direct relationship between the degree of stability of the residues and the emissions of N₂O as evidenced by the correlation between N₂O and CO₂ emission (Figure 12). These results are in agreement with those of Gálvez et al. (2012), showing higher N₂O emission associated with more degradable material. The only remarkable exception to this general behaviour was recorded in the case of VC that showed the highest amount of N₂O emissions despite to be a material more stable than SCG and VC. The peculiarity of VC with respect to the other amendments is underlined by the fact that the correlation between cumulative CO₂ and N₂O emission present a R² of 0.51 considering all the amendments. The same correlation without VC has a R² of 0.97. The peculiar behaviour of BC could be explained by the fact that VC presented a low C/N ratio (7 - Table 4). Low C/N ratio favours N mineralization as showed by values of extractable N and nitrate and therefore the release of available N that is one of the factors conducive to the formation of N₂O in aerobic conditions (Wrage et al., 2001).

Figure 12. Relationships between cumulative emissions of CO₂-C and N₂O-N. Dashed blue line represents a correlation considering all the amendments, while continue red line is a correlation not considering vermicompost (blue marker).

The lowest values of N₂O emissions were recorded with biochar. Moreover, an increase in the temperature of pyrolysis from 270 to 400 °C causes a further decrease in N₂O emissions. These results suggest that pyrolysis decrease the emission potential of SCG and is in agreement with previous findings about the fact that pyrolysis leading to an extremely stable material and significantly decreasing the N₂O emissions of the original feedstocks.

3.3. Conclusions

All transformations applied to SCG generate by-products that are quite different from the original SCG and with very distinctive chemical properties. A clear relationship has been shown between the properties of the amendments and their effects on the C and N cycles, nutrients availability, microbial biomass pool and GHG emissions. Spent coffee grounds and hydrochars are bio-residues that stimulate soil biological activity, due to the fact that they contain easily decomposable carbonaceous molecules. The hydrothermal carbonization process (generator of hydrochars) accentuates this characteristic. As a consequence, SCG and hydrochars lead in the short and medium term to N immobilization, lower organic C conservation in the soil and to CO₂ emissions in the atmosphere. The pyrolysis of SCG, which gives rise to biochars, removes much of the easily decomposable C from these residues, leading to less N immobilization and greater fixation of organic C in the soil. Therefore, the two thermal transformation pathways lead to wastes with divergent characteristics and effects on the soil. The vermicomposting of SCG generates a product with stable carbonaceous molecules, but with a high content of different forms of N. It is the only one of the SCG by-products that does not generate N immobilization and can even be considered as a N fertilizer. For that concerning N₂O emissions all the materials caused very low increases with emissions factors by far lower (< 0.01 % of added N) in comparison to mineral fertilizers. However, results showed that N₂O emissions were affected by the properties of the materials, namely their decomposability and N content.

The results of the present study showed the potential of SCG by-products as effective organic amendment. Moreover, depending on their properties, they can be used to fulfil specific agronomic and ecosystem service functions.

4. Field experiment

4.1. Materials and Methods

4.1.1. Experimental setup

The field experiment was set up at the AGES (Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety) experimental station in Grabenegg, Lower Austria, focusing on silage maize (*Zea mays*) and spring wheat cultivation. The soil was amended with compost and biochar, and six different treatments were tested (Table 6) using a randomized plot design consisting of 5x8 m plots, with 4 plots for each treatment (Figure 13).

Table 6: Soil treatment in Short-Term Experiment.

Variant	Treatment
1	Control (no fertilization)
2	NPK-fertilization (175 kg N, 90 kg P ₂ O ₅ , 225 kg K ₂ O/ha)
3	Biowaste compost (35 t ha ⁻¹ to ca. 350 N kg ha ⁻¹)
4	NPK (175 kg N, 90 kg P ₂ O ₅ , 225 kg K ₂ O/ha) + biochar (7t/ha hardwood biochar)
5	Compost (35 t/ha equivalent to ca. 350kg N/ha) + biochar (7t/ha hardwood biochar)
6	Biogas digestate: from waste plant (66 t ha ⁻¹ to ca. 350kg N/ha)

more and more available in developing countries and this low-cost method could be supportive for a more climate-friendly management of farmlands.

This method is based on an acid trap placed a semi-open static chamber made of a PET (polyethylene terephthalate)-bottle with a cut bottom which then is fixed with an iron wire at the top to avoid wetting by precipitation (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**15). The acid trap is made of a filter paper stripe sealed with polytetrafluorethylen (PTFE) and immersed in an acidic solution of 2.5 M KHSO₄ and 5% glycerol within a 20 mL vial. Volatilised NH₃ within the chamber gets then absorbed by the acid and gets solubilized as NH₄⁺ (Araújo et al., 2009; Martins et al., 2021).

The chambers were left on the field and the acid traps were changed every week. The solutions within the 20 mL vials were neutralized with a NaOH solution and then the NH₄⁺ concentration was measured photometrically based on the method of Hood-Nowotny et al., 2010.

Figure 15: NH₃-measurements: semi-open static chamber.

To assess NH₃ trapping efficiency, a comparison was made between data from semi-open static chambers and NH₃ in ambient air using a *Picarro* analyser. Soil cores (70 mm in diameter, 72 mm in depth) were collected 19 days post-fertilization, a period when N₂O emissions and NH₃ volatilization captured by the chambers were elevated. These cores were subsequently analysed in the laboratory using the *Picarro* device (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**16). However, due to a delay in measurements—approximately seven months of storage at 4°C—no NH₃ volatilization rates were observed.

Figure 16: NH₃-measurements with Picarro ammonia in ambient air analyser.

4.1.4. Soil measurements

Soil parameters were analysed using K₂SO₄ extracts, which were measured photometrically following the method of Hood-Nowotny et al. (2010). A new pipetting robot from Opentrons (Figure 17) was introduced to automate the process. Custom protocols were written in Python, enabling high-throughput sample processing and significantly reducing manual pipetting time. Additionally, the system is relatively cost-effective.

Figure 17: Opentrons pipetting robot.

4.2. Most relevant results

The first year of experimentation (2022), a fast increase of NO₃⁻ and NH₄⁺ in soil by NPK fertilisation and biodigestate treatment was observed (Figure 18). For compost increase was rather little. Biochar had an effect on the emissions and on the soil-nitrogen. NO₃⁻ and NH₄⁺ decreased faster in soil for biochar treatments and had a significant effect on the gaseous N-losses.

Figure 18: Nitrogen data: A: soil-NO₃⁻, soil-NH₄⁺, C: N₂O emissions; D: NH₃ volatilisation; E: soil moisture.

A substantial mitigation effects due to biochar application was observed (Figure 19 and 20). N₂O emissions were reduced to 36 % for NPK + biochar and 53 % for compost + biochar treatments. Also, NH₃ volatilisation was mitigated substantial: 56 % for NPK + biochar and 40 % for compost+ biochar.

Figure 19: N₂O emissions maize (season 2022).

Figure 20: NH₃ volatilisation maize (season 2022).

Figure 21: Soil nitrate maize (season 2022).

Figure 22: Soil ammonium maize (season 2022).

In 2023, spring wheat was cultivated instead of corn, as was done in 2022. For the NPK treatments additional fertiliser (N, 60 kg ha⁻¹; P, 30 kg ha⁻¹; K, 40 kg ha⁻¹; Ca, 18 kg ha⁻¹) was applied. For compost and biodigestate treatments no additional fertilisation took place.

Mitigation effects of biochar on N₂O and NH₃ emissions were also observed (Figure 23). The N₂O emissions in general were much lower than 2022 since the total amount of fertilizer was only 60 N kg ha⁻¹ instead of 175 kg N ha⁻¹ in 2022. NH₃ volatilisation was reduced by 40 %.

Figure 23: N₂O emissions and NH₃ volatilisation wheat (season 2023).

A significant reduction in soil NO₃⁻ and NH₄⁺ content was observed compared to 2022 (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Soil nitrate and ammonium, wheat (season 2023).

In the season 2024, again silage maize was cultivated. Biochar’s mitigation on N₂O emissions and NH₃ volatilisation could be further enhanced by the new application of biochar (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**25 and **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**26). Biochar reduced the N₂O emissions by 54% for NPK fertilisation and 18% for compost. Compost had relatively low emission rates compared to the year 2022, however. NH₃ volatilisation was reduced by biochar by 65% for NPK and 49% for compost.

Figure 25: N₂O emissions maize (season 2024).

Figure 26: NH₃ volatilisation maize (season 2024).

The pattern of an immobilisation effect was not so clear observable than in the previous two years (Figure 27 and 28). This might be caused by frequent rain events in the first month after the application of the fertilisation events. Further, changes in the stoichiometric N₂O/N₂ ratio for the denitrification pathway could also be responsible for reduced N₂O release (Cayuela et al., 2014).

Figure 27: Soil nitrate maize (season 2024).

Figure 28: Soil ammonium maize (season 2024).

4.3. Conclusions

Two mechanisms are hypothesized to contribute to the mitigation of N₂O emissions: (I) the immobilization of NO₃⁻ and NH₄⁺ in the soil due to the presence of biochar, as observed in the field soils, and (II) the facilitation of complete denitrification, converting N₂O to N₂. The literature provides substantial support for the second mechanism associated with biochar.

List of references

Abdullahi, Y.A., Akunna, J.C., White, N.A., Hallett, P.D., Wheatley, R. (2008). Investigating the effects of anaerobic and aerobic post-treatment on quality and stability of organic fraction of municipal solid waste as soil amendment. *Bioresource Technology*, 99(18), 8631-8636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2008.04.027>

Al Seadi, T., Lukehurst, C. (2012). Quality management of digestate from biogas plants used as fertiliser. International Energy Agency (IEA) Bioenergy; Task 37: Energy from Biogas. Available online: <http://www.iea-biogas.net>

Araújo, E., Marsola, T., Miyazawa, M., Soares, L., Urquiaga, S., Boddey, R., Alves, B. (2009). Calibration of a semi-opened static chamber for the quantification of volatilized ammonia from soil. *Pesquisa Agropecuária Brasileira*, 44, 769–776. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-204X2009000700018>

Caporaso, J.G., Lauber, C.L., Costello, E.K., Berg-Lyons, D., Gonzalez, A., Stombaugh, J., Knights, D., Gajer, P., Ravel, J., Fierer, N., Gordon, J.I., Knight, R. (2011). Moving pictures of the human microbiome. *Genome Biology*, 12: 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/gb-2011-12-5-r50>

Cayuela, M.L., Van Zwieten, L., Singh, B.P., Jeffery, S., Roig, A., Sánchez-Monedero, M.A. (2014). Biochar's role in mitigating soil nitrous oxide emissions: A review and meta-analysis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 191: 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.10.009>

Cervera-Mata, A., Delgado, G., Fernández-Arteaga, A., Fornasier, F., Mondini C. (2022) Spent coffee grounds by-products and their influence on soil C–N dynamics. *Journal of Environmental Management* 302, Part B, 114075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114075>

Denman, S.E., Tomkins, N.W., McSweeney, C.S. (2007). Quantitation and diversity analysis of ruminal methanogenic populations in response to the antimethanogenic compound bromochloromethane. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 62: 313-322. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6941.2007.00394.x>

Galvez, A., Sinicco, T., Cayuela, M.L., Mingorance, M.D., Fornasier, F., Mondini, C. (2012). Short term effects of bioenergy by-products on soil C and N dynamics, nutrient availability and biochemical properties. *Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment*, 160, 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2011.06.015>

Gomez, J.D., Denef, K., Stewart, C.E., Zheng, J., Cotrufo, M.F. (2014). Biochar addition rate influences soil microbial abundance and activity in temperate soils. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 65: 28-39. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12097>

Green, T.R., Popa, R. (2011). Turnover of carbohydrate-rich vegetal matter during microaerobic composting and after amendment in soil. *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 165: 270-278. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12010-011-9249-4>

Hood-Nowotny, R., Umana, N.H.-N., Inselbacher, E., Oswald-Lachouani, P., Wanek, W. (2010). Alternative Methods for Measuring Inorganic, Organic, and Total Dissolved Nitrogen in Soil. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 74(3), 1018–1027. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2009.0389>

He, Y., Zhou, X., Jiang, L., Li, M., Du, Z., Zhou, G., Shao, J., Wang, X., Xu, Z., Bai, S.H., Wallace, H., Xu, C. (2017). Effects of biochar application on soil greenhouse gas fluxes: A meta-analysis. *GCB Bioenergy*, 9: 743-755. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12376>

Hung, C.H., Cheng, C.H., Cheng, L.H., Liang, C.M., Lin, C.Y. (2008). Application of *Clostridium*-specific PCR primers on the analysis of dark fermentation hydrogen-producing bacterial community. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 33: 1586-1592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2007.09.037>

IUSS Working Group WRB (2014). World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International Soil Classification System for Naming Soils and Creating Legends for Soil Maps. World Soil Resources Reports No. 106 2014. FAO, Rome.

Kammann, C., Ratering, S., Eckhard, C., Müller, C. (2012). Biochar and hydrochar effects on greenhouse gas (carbon dioxide, nitrous oxide, and methane) fluxes from soils. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 41, 1052-1066. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2011.0132>

Kolb, S., Knief, C., Stubner, S., Conrad, R. (2003). Quantitative detection of methanotrophs in soil by novel *pmoA*-targeted real-time PCR assays. *Applied Environmental Microbiology*, 69: 2423-2429. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.69.5.2423-2429.2003>

Lagomarsino, A., Valagussa, M., Becagli, C., Rocchi, F., Tosca, A., Pastorelli, R. (2024). Effectiveness of biochar in the short-term abatement of GHGs and NH₃ emissions from digestate and slurry. *Scientific Journal Biology & Life Sciences*.

Martins, M.R., Sarkis, L.F., Guareschi, R.F., Santos, C.A., Sant'Anna, S.A.C., Zaman, M., Jantalia, C.P., Alves, B.J.R., Boddey, R.M., Araujo, E.S., Urquiaga, S. (2021). A simple and easy method to measure ammonia volatilization: Accuracy under field conditions. *Pedosphere*, 31(2), 255–264. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160\(20\)60077-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160(20)60077-7)

Mickan, B.S., Ren, A.T., Buhmann, C.H., Ghadouani, A., Solaiman, Z.M., Jenkins, S., Pang, J., Ryan, M.H. (2022). Closing the circle for urban food waste anaerobic digestion: The use of digestate and biochar on plant growth in potting soil. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 347: 131071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131071>

Miranda, K.M., Espey, M.G., Wink, D.A. (2001). A rapid, simple spectrophotometric method for simultaneous detection of nitrate and nitrite. *Nitric Oxide* 5(1), 62-71. <https://doi.org/10.1006/niox.2000.0319>

Mondini, C., Cayuela, M.L., Sinicco, T., Fornasier, F., Galvez, A., Sánchez-Monedero, M.A. (2018). Soil C storage potential of exogenous organic matter at regional level (Italy) under climate change simulated by RothC model modified for amended soils. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 6: 144. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2018.00144>.

Muyzer, G., De Waal, E.C.; Uitterlinden, A. (1993). Profiling of complex microbial populations by denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis analysis of polymerase chain reaction-amplified genes coding for 16S rRNA. *Applied Environmental Microbiology*, 59: 695-700. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.59.3.695-700.1993>

Nichols, K.L., del Grosso, S.J., Derner, J.D., Follett, R.F., Archibeque, S.L., Delgado, J.A., Paustian, K.H. (2018). Nitrous oxide and ammonia emissions from cattle excreta on shortgrass steppe. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 47(3), 419–426. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2017.12.0463>

Pastorelli, R., Valboa, G., Lagomarsino, A., Fabiani, A., Simoncini, S., Zaghi, M., Vignozzi, N. (2021). Recycling biogas digestate from energy crops: effects on soil properties and crop productivity. *Applied Science*, 11: 750. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11020750>

Pastorelli, R., Casagli, A., Rocchi, F., Tampio, E., Laaksonen, I., Becagli, C., Lagomarsino, A. (2024). Effects of anaerobic digestates and biochar amendments on soil health, greenhouse gas emissions, and microbial communities: A mesocosm study. *Applied Sciences*, 14: 1917. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14051917>

Plaimart, J., Acharya, K., Mrozik, W., Davenport, R.J., Vinitnantharat, S., Werner, D. (2021). Coconut husk biochar amendment enhances nutrient retention by suppressing nitrification in agricultural soil following anaerobic digestate application. *Environmental Pollution*, 268: 115684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115684>

Pulvirenti, A., Ronga, D., Zaghi, M., Tomasselli, A.R., Mannella, L., Pecchioni, N. (2015). Pelleting is a successful method to eliminate the presence of *Clostridium* spp. from the digestate of biogas plants. *Biomass Bioenergy*, 81: 479-482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2015.08.008>

Ren, A.T., Abbott, L.K., Chen, Y., Xiong, Y.C., Mickan, B.S. (2022). Nutrient recovery from anaerobic digestion of food waste: Impacts of digestate on plant growth and rhizosphere bacterial community composition and potential function in ryegrass. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 56: 973–989. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-020-01477-6>

Singh, R., Paritosh, K., Pareek, N., Vivekanand, V. (2022). Integrated system of anaerobic digestion and pyrolysis for valorization of agricultural and food waste towards circular bioeconomy. *Bioresource Technology*, 360: 127596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127596>

Sommer, S.G., Kjellerup, V., Kristjansen, O. (1992). Determination of total ammonium nitrogen in pig and cattle slurry: sample preparation and analysis. *Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica B-Plant Soil Sciences*, 42, 146-151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064719209417969>

Tampio, E., Laaksonen, I., Rimhanen, K., Honkala, N., Laakso, J., Soinne, H., Rasa, K. (2024). Effect of manure co-digestion on methane production, carbon retention, and fertilizer value of digestate. *Science of the Total Environment*, 927: 172083. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172083>

Tang, Z., Zhang, L., He, N., Gong, D., Gao, H., Ma, Z., Fu, L., Zhao, M., Wang, H., Wang, C., Zheng, W., Zhang, W. (2021). Soil bacterial community as impacted by addition of rice straw and biochar. *Scientific Reports*, 11: 22185. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-99001-9>

Thies, J.E., Rillig, M.C., Graber, E.R. (2015). Biochar effects on the abundance, activity and diversity of the soil biota. In *Biochar for environmental management: science, technology and implementation*; Lehmann, J. and Joseph, S., Eds.; Routledge, Taylor & Francis; 2015, vol. 2, pp. 327-389.

Thomson, A.J., Giannopoulos, G., Pretty, J., Baggs, E.M., Richardson, D.J. (2012). Biological sources and sinks of nitrous oxide and strategies to mitigate emissions. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B Biological Science*, 367: 1157–1168. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2011.0415>

Throbäck, I.N., Enwall, K., Jarvis, Å., Hallin, S. (2004). Reassessing PCR primers targeting *nirS*, *nirK* and *nosZ* genes for community surveys of denitrifying bacteria with DGGE. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 49: 401-417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.femsec.2004.04.011>

Vance, E.D., Brookes, P.C., Jenkinson, D.S. (1987). An extraction method for measuring soil microbial biomass. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 19, 703–707. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717\(87\)90052-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717(87)90052-6)

Van Veldhoven, P.P., Mannaerts, G.P. (1987). Inorganic and organic phosphate measurements in the nanomolar range. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 161, 45-48. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697\(87\)90649-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697(87)90649-X)

Wrage, N., Velthof, G.L., Van Beusichem, M.L., Oenema, O. (2001). Role of nitrifier denitrification in the production of nitrous oxide. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 33, 1723-1732. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(01\)00096-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(01)00096-7)

Xu, M., Schnorr, J., Keibler, B., Simon, H.M. (2012). Comparative analysis of 16S rRNA and *amoA* genes from archaea selected with organic and inorganic amendments in enrichment culture. *Applied Environmental Microbiology*, 78: 2137-2146. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.06845-11>

Xu, H., Cai, A., Wu, D., Liang, G., Xiao, J., Xu, M., Colinet, G., Zhang, W. (2021). Effects of biochar application on crop productivity, soil carbon sequestration, and global warming potential controlled by biochar C:N ratio and soil pH: A global meta-analysis. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 213: 105125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2021.105125>

Zhao, L., Sun, Z.-F., Pan, X.-W., Tan, J.-Y., Yang, S.-S., Wu, J.-T., Chen, C., Yuan, Y., Ren, N.-Q. (2023). Sewage sludge derived biochar for environmental improvement: Advances, challenges, and solutions. *Water Research*, 18: 100167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wroa.2023.100167>

Zhu, M., Zhang, L., Zheng, L., Zhuo, Y., Xu, J., He, Y. (2018). Typical soil redox processes in pentachlorophenol polluted soil following biochar addition. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 9: 579. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.00579>

Zwiehner, J., Liszt, K., Handschur, M., Lassl, C., Lapin, A., Haslberger, A.G. (2009). Combined PCR-DGGE fingerprinting and quantitative-PCR indicates shifts in fecal population sizes and diversity of *Bacteroides*; bifidobacteria and *Clostridium* cluster IV in institutionalized elderly. *Experimental Gerontology*, 44: 440-446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exger.2009.04.002>

